

(M^+ 468); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1735, 1260. The other hydrolysis product was identified as *p*-methoxy-*trans*-cinnamic acid (or *p*-coumaric acid)¹¹ isolated as its methyl ester from CHCl_3 -petrol as needles, m.p. 90°.

A greenish yellow solid was obtained from the 10% methanolic chloroform eluates of the main chromatogram which on repeated chromatographies over silica gel, furnished ellagic acid-4,4'-dimethyl ether (V), crystallising from CHCl_3 -MeOH in pale yellow globules (0.001%), m.p. 298-300°, $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_8$ (M^+ 330); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3080 cm^{-1} (br, OH), 1708 (lactone), 1595, 1565 and 1470 (aromatic); λ_{\max} (EtOH) 254 nm and 376 nm which shifted to 274 nm and 434 nm respectively in alkali. On treatment with $\text{Ac}_2\text{O/Py}$ (r.t. 24 hr), (V) gave an acetate (VI) from CHCl_3 -petrol as needles, m.p. 290-92°, $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4$ (M^+ 414); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1770 cm^{-1} (phenolic acetate), 1735, 1695, 1470, 1240. The $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectrum (CDCl_3 , δ) of the acetate (VI) showed three singlets: at 7.88 due to two aromatic protons at C-5 and C-5'; at 4.26 assignable to two aryloxy methyls at C-4 and C-4' and at 2.40 attributed to the two acetoxy methyls at C-3 and C-3'. The failure of (V) to give positive Greissmayer reaction¹² also suggested that its two hydroxyl groups are at C-3 and C-3'. The mass spectrum of the acetate (VI) showed ion peaks 414 (M^+ , 6.7%), 386 (5.3), 372 (13.3), 344 (20), 330 (100), 286 (6.7), 302 (5.3). The early benzene eluate fractions of the main chromatogram on evaporation afforded a greenish white solid which on further chromatography furnished β -amyrin, crystallised from chloroform-petrol as needles (15 mg), m.p. 199°, $[\alpha]_D^{+80}$; acetate ($\text{Ac}_2\text{O/Py}$), m.p. 182°.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to express their sincere thanks to Mr. D. F. Dance (Stirling University, UK) for the mass spectral measurements, to Mr. A. Acharya of this Department for the nmr spectral analyses and to the CSIR, New Delhi for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship to one of them (A. B.).

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Terpenoid Constituents of *Boehmeria platyphylla* Don. : Sodium Borohydride Reduction of 5 α -Stigmastan-3,6-dione†

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Manuscript received 23 March 1981, accepted 9 June 1981

BOEHMERIA *platyphylla* Don.¹ (fam. Urticaceae) is generally a long shrub growing in the outer Himalayas upto 7,000 ft, Khasia Hills, Bangladesh, South India and Srilanka and is also distributed in Malay Island, China, Japan and Africa. Earlier works² on the basic components of the plant revealed the presence of 3,4-dimethoxy- ω -(2-piperidyl) acetophenone, cyptopleurine (a phenanthraquinolizidine alkaloid) and a *secophenanthraquinolizidine* alkaloid of undetermined structure. There is no report of previous work on the non basic constituents of this plant although several sister species have been known to elaborate a number of triterpenes³, lignans⁴, flavones⁵ and fatty acids⁶. The present paper describes the isolation and characterisation of 5 α -stigmastan-3, 6-dione (I) (yield 0.0035%), pomolic acid (II) (0.005%), oleanolic acid (0.0073%), lupeol (0.004%) and β -sitosterol (0.012%) from the leaves and twigs of *B. platyphylla* and study on the NaBH_4 reduction products of I. To our knowledge, the present isolation of 5 α -stigmastan-3,6-dione constitutes its second occurrence in nature, the first isolation being from the twigs of *Metasequoia glyptostroboides*⁸.

Air dried and powdered leaves and twigs of *B. platyphylla* was Soxhletted with light petrol (60-80°) and chloroform in succession for 50 hrs each. The residues obtained by concentration of the extracts under reduced pressure showed the presence of only trace amount of alkaloidal constituents which was not separated. The residue from the light petrol extract was chromatographed over silica gel, elution being carried out with solvents and solvent mixtures of increasing polarity.

The concentrate of the light petrol-benzene (1:1) eluate fractions upon several rechromatographies over silica gel afforded lupeol, crystallising from CHCl_3 -MeOH in colourless needles, m.p. 212°, $[\alpha]_D^{+24.4}$ (CHCl_3 , c 0.068); acetate, m.p. 217°, $[\alpha]_D^{+41.5}$ (CHCl_3 , c 0.075), its identity being confirmed by direct comparison (m.m.p., co-tlc and ir) with an authentic sample.

The early benzene eluate fractions afforded β -sitosterol crystallising from CHCl_3 -MeOH in flakes, m.p. 137° alone and also upon admixture with an authentic sample.

The residue obtained from the later benzene eluate fractions and benzene- CHCl_3 (1:1) eluate fractions on extensive rechromatography over silica

† Part XXI in the series Terpenoids and Related Compounds', For Part XX see B. TALAPATRA, A. BASAK and S. K. TALAPATRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **58**, 814.

I: $R^1, R^2=R^3, R^4=O$
 III: $R^1=R^2=OH, R^3=R^4=H$
 IV: $R^2=R^3=OH, R^1=R^4=H$

II: $R^1=R^2=H$
 V: $R^1=COCH_3, R^2=H$
 VI: $R^1=H, R^2=CH_3$
 VII: $R^1=COCH_3, R^2=CH_3$

gel using $CHCl_3$ as the eluent afforded 5 α -stigmastan-3,6-dione(I), crystallising from $CHCl_3$ -light petrol in colourless needles, m.p. 198-99°, $[\alpha]_D + 8.3^\circ$ ($CHCl_3, c 0.098$), no colouration in Liebermann-Burchard test as well as with TNM; λ_{max} (EtOH) 286 nm ($\epsilon = 40$); ν_{max}^{KBr} 1713-1705 cm^{-1} (more than one CO in six-membered rings); PMR (80 MHz, $CDCl_3$) (δ) 0.64, 0.74, 0.84 and 0.90 (18H, six methyl groups), 1.94-2.53 (7H, *m*, three active $-CH_2-$ and one active $-CH-$); 5.05-5.15 ($\sim \frac{1}{2}H$, *m*, the olefinic proton of the enol forms of the molecule); MS: important ion peaks at *m/e* 428 (M^+ , 100%), 287 ($M^+ - C_{10}H_{21}$, 40.5) and 245 ($M^+ - C_{10}H_{21} - C_2H_5$, 66.7). The α -nature of H-5 (i.e., *trans* locking of A/B rings) was evident as the compound did not undergo any isomerisation on heating with HCl-AcOH or EtOH-NaOH. The identity of this compound with 5 α -stigmastan-3,6-dione(I) was confirmed by direct comparison (m.m.p., ir, co-tlc) with an authentic sample obtained by a partial synthesis from β -sitosterol through $CrO_3/HOAc$ oxidation (1 hr) followed by Zn dust-HOAc reduction (4 hrs)⁷.

Reduction of I with $NaBH_4$ in MeOH gave two diastereoisomeric diols in the approximate ratio 9 : 1. The melting points of the major diol (204-5°) and its diacetate (113-14°) indicate that it is stigmastan-3 β , 6 β -diol(III), the only product of the catalytic reduction of I⁷. The appearance of the one-proton ill-resolved broad signals at δ 3.65 ($w_{\frac{1}{2}} \sim 36$ Hz) and 3.75 ($w_{\frac{1}{2}} \sim 11$ Hz) in the pmr spectrum of the major diol and those at δ 4.85 ($w_{\frac{1}{2}} \sim 36$ Hz) and 4.9 ($w_{\frac{1}{2}} \sim 11$ Hz) in the pmr spectrum of its diacetate indicates the axial and hence α -nature of H-3 and the equatorial and hence α -nature of H-6 in both the compounds. The minor diol was found to be a hitherto unknown compound stigmastan-3 α , 6 β -diol(IV), m.p. 200-201°, from its pmr spectrum in which the carbonyl methine protons (H-3 and H-6) appear at δ 3.75 ($w_{\frac{1}{2}} \sim 11$ Hz) and 4.2 ($w_{\frac{1}{2}} \sim 11.5$ Hz); the smaller $w_{\frac{1}{2}}$ values indicate the equatorial nature of both of them showing the structure of the minor diol as IV.

The dark brown residue obtained from the $CHCl_3$ -MeOH (97 : 3) eluate fractions on repeated chromatography over silica gel followed by crystallisations from EtOH afforded oleanolic acid in

colourless needles, m.p. 302-4°; acetate, m.p. 255-57°, $[\alpha]_D + 71.4^\circ$ ($CHCl_3, c 0.054$), identified by direct comparison (m.m.p., co-tlc and ir) with an authentic sample.

The residue from the $CHCl_3$ extract was chromatographed over silica gel in the usual way. The black jelly-like residue obtained from the $CHCl_3$ -MeOH (95 : 5) eluate fractions on repeated chromatography over the same adsorbent followed by crystallisations from ethanol afforded pomolic acid (19 α -hydroxyursolic acid)(II) in colourless needles m.p. 284-85°, $[\alpha]_D + 33^\circ$ ($CHCl_3, c 0.030$), ν_{max}^{KBr} 3680-3320 (OH) and 1685 cm^{-1} (COOH). On acetylation (Ac_2O/Py , room temp.) pomolic acid formed a monoacetate(V), m.p. 245-48°, $[\alpha]_D + 40.8^\circ$ ($CHCl_3, c 0.066$), ν_{max}^{KBr} 3620-3390 (OH), 1725 and 1235 cm^{-1} (acetate); PMR (80 MHz, $CDCl_3$) (δ) 0.68, 0.81 and 0.90 (15H, five methyl groups), 1.15 (3H, *s*, CH_3 on C-14), 1.20 (3H, *s*, CH_3 on C-19), 2.00 (3H, *s*, $-OCOCH_3$), 2.50 (1H, br. *s*, H-18), 4.51 (1H, *dd*, $J = 8.5$ and 6.5 Hz, H-3) and 5.32 (1H, br. *s*, H-12); MS: important ion peaks at *m/e* 512 (M^+), 468, 454, 439, 411, 396, 264, 249, 246, 231, 218, 201, 190, 187, 175 and 146. On treatment with CH_3N_2 , II formed methyl pomolate(VI), m.p. 129° [crystallised from light petrol (40-60°)], $[\alpha]_D + 37.6^\circ$ ($CHCl_3, c 0.082$). Acetylation of VI gave acetyl methyl pomolate(VII), m.p. 238-39°, $[\alpha]_D + 44.6^\circ$ ($CHCl_3, c 0.076$), VII was also obtained by treatment of the monoacetate V with CH_3N_2 . Pomolic acid was identified from the above physical and spectral data and its identity was confirmed by comparison of the ir and pmr spectra of acetyl methyl pomolate(VII) with those of an authentic sample (acetyl methyl benthamate)⁸. In addition to pomolic acid the $CHCl_3$ extract also afforded further amounts of 5 α -stigmastan-3,6-dione(I), oleanolic acid and β -sitosterol.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to thank Dr. N. Murofushi (Tokyo University) and Mr. D. F. Dance (University of Stirling, UK) for mass spectral measurements, Mr. A. Acharya of this Department for pmr spectral measurements and Professor A. G. Gonzalez